

EXAMINATION OF TRAINER COMMUNICATION SKILLS PERCEIVED BY ATHLETES ACCORDING TO SPORT FIELDS

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Abstract:

This research is a descriptive study that aims to examine coach communication skills perceived by athletes according to branches. A total of 767 active athletes (517 male, 250 female) in Gaziantep were chosen as the study group on a volunteer basis. Quantitative data were collected using “Coach Communication Scale in Football” developed by Abakay and Kuru (2009) (in order to obtain research data). Data collected from the study group were analyzed and reported according to the athletes’ demographics and other variables discussed in the research. The data obtained from the scale were first transferred to the electronic environment and then calculated using SPSS 22.0 package program. Arithmetic mean, One-Way ANOVA, Spearman’s rho (rs) correlation test and t-test were used for analyzing the data, for comparing the mean scores in the unrelated measures, for examining the relationship between the variables, and for Independent samples, respectively. In conclusion, in this study we conducted to determine the coach communication skills perceived by the team – and individual athletes and to reveal the differences in terms of various variables, it was found that this ratio differed significantly between individual athletes while the coach communication skills perceived by two athlete groups were high. Our findings showed that the perceived coach communication skills tended to decline in situations where the sporting history of individual athletes increased. It has been established that their communication skills improved in the situations where educational background enhanced although there was also no gender difference in both sports groups. It has been concluded that the perceived coach communication skills also improved in the situations where it would

tend to increase in some variables such as athlete's age, coach's age and duration of training with the same coach.

Keywords: individual, team, trainer, communication

1. Introduction

The main aim of the athletes and coaches in sports environment is to obtain high performance in the competitions and to ensure the continuation of this performance. Therefore, ensuring high performance is both an automatic process and it also includes a good orientation and a correct psychological preparation (Abakay 2010).

The communication of the athletes with their coaches is a matter that is between two individuals and included in the scope of interpersonal communication. Therefore, we can say that the behaviors of the individuals against each other in the prepared situations include the laughter; physical expressions, gestures, mimics and verbal and non-verbal expressions cover inter-personal communication type (Alıncak 2016; Lazar 2001).

In the manner of approaching of coaches to the athletes, they must have an aim to establish an efficient and healthy cooperation (Alıncak, 2017). Anyway, while the behavior of the coaches is strengthening the connection in communicative sense, it will help to remove the factors which may adversely affect the performances of the athletes (Alıncak 2016; Güven 1996).

In the communication between the athlete and the coach, concepts such as the messages that the coaches want to convey to the athletes, the outlooks and approaches to the events, the leadership styles of the coaches and the understanding of the game reflected to the athletes also reveal the coaching philosophies of the coaches. The philosophy of coaching is expressed as a specific factor in the content of the decisions taken on the team, what strategic and tactical behaviors are to be taught, how the training should be programmed, what methods are used in disciplining the athletes and what roles should be given to individuals in putting in a good performance (Ayan et al 2017; Cengiz 2009). Coaches must first communicate well and effectively with the athletes in order to be able to realize their philosophy. Because an effective communication between the coach and the athlete is considered as an important factor in increasing the performance of the athlete individually and the team (Abakay 2010).

In the relationship between the athletes and the coach, if it is thought that both observable and perceived coach behaviors affect the performance of athletes, it is stated that in the investigation of the coach-athlete relationships in terms of perceived

behaviors will offer important information for successful or effective coaching (Alıncak et al 2015; Altıntaş et al., 2012).

Individual communication skills that are important in daily life or sports environment is a matter that should be emphasized and not to be ignored in terms of the researchers who work in the psychosocial field of sport. In this study performed in the light of this information, determining whether there are differences of coach communication skills perceived by the athletes in terms of the status of the athletes' branches constitutes the main aim of the study. It has also been seen as an important issue in the research problems of differences in the coach communication skills perceived by the athletes in the factors such as the athletes' learning situations, their ages, the years of playing sports, the duration of coaching and the duration of coaching of coaches.

2. Method

2.1 Method of Research

This research is a descriptive study aimed at examining the coach communication skills perceived by the athletes according to the branches.

2.2 Universe and Sampling

A total of 767 (517 male, 250 female) athletes who were active sportsmen in Gaziantep was selected as athletes research group. Some personal characteristics of the research group are given in table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of personal characteristics of the study group

		n	%
Branch status	Team	357	33.8
	Individual	410	38.9
Gender	Male	517	49.0
	Female	250	23.7
Educational Status of the Athlete	Primary school	6	.6
	High School	267	25.3
	License	437	41.4
	Master	57	5.4
Year of doing sport	1-4 years	199	18.9
	5-8 years	282	26.7
	9-12 years	188	17.8
	13 + years	98	9.3

2.3 Data Collection Techniques

In the collection of research data, "Coach Communication Scale in Football" developed by Abakay and Kuru (2009) was used and it is a scale composed of 28 items developed by five-point likert scale, evaluated over the total point and prepared to determine the communication skills of the coaches perceived by the athletes by applying to the athletes. Scores to be obtained from the scale can range from 28 to 140 points. High scores on the scale indicate that the coach has high communication skills. As a result of applying the scale only to footballers, Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was determined as 0.946 and the Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was determined to be 0.944 as a result of the reliability analysis for this study which was conducted in different status and branches.

2.4 Statistical Analysis of Data

The data obtained from the scale were first transferred to the computer environment and then calculated by using the SPSS 22.0 package program. Variant analysis One-Way ANOVA was used to compared mean scores in independent measurements Independent samples t-test) (Karagöz and Ekici 2004) and Spearman'srho (rs) correlation test was used to examine the relationship between two variables (Gamgam 1998).

3. Findings

In this part of the study, variance analysis showing the total scores of individual and team athletes obtained from Futbolda Coach Communication Scale, differences on branch status, gender, age, years of sports making, years of training, years of coaching, coaching duration and coaching duration correlations were found.

Table 3: Comparison of coach communication skills perceived by the research group in terms of branch status

Branch	N	Mean	Sd.	t	p
Team	357	110.43	19.80	-4.916	000
Individual	408	116.77	15.22		

In Table 3, the comparison of coach communication skills perceived by the research group in terms of branch status is given. Accordingly, there was a significant difference in favor of individual athletes ($p < 0.05$).

Table 4: Comparison of perceived coach communication skills between male and female athletes in terms of branch status

	Branch Status	N	Mean	sd.	t	p
Male	Team	214	112.00	17.88	-3.128	.002
	Individual	303	116.69	15.09		
Female	Team	143	108.09	22.23	-3.726	.000
	Individual	107	117.02	15.64		

In Table 4, the comparison of coach communication skills perceived by athletes in terms of branch status is given. According to this, male and female athletes have significant differences in favor of individual athletes ($p < 0.05$).

Table 5: Comparison of perceived coach communication skills in team and individual athletes in terms of gender variable

	Gender	N	Mean	Sd.	t	p
Team	Male	214	112.00	17.88	1.834	0.068
	Female	143	108.09	22.23		
Individual	Male	303	116.69	15.09	-.191	.849
	Female	107	117.02	15.64		

In Table 5, the comparison of the coach communication skills perceived by athletes in terms of gender variation is given. According to this, there was no difference in gender variation in coach communication skills perceived by team and individual athletes ($p > 0.05$).

Table 6: Comparisons of perceived coach communication skills among athletes in terms of the variable of athlete status

		KT	sd	KO	F	p	Significant difference
Team	Inter-groups	2498.693	3	832.898	2.145	.024	3-1
	In-group	137071.010	353	388.303			3-2
							4-1
	Total	139569.703	356				4-2
Individual	Inter-groups	620.754	3	206.918	.893	.015	3-1
	In-group	94093.151	406	231.757			3-2
							4-1
	Total	94713.905	409				4-2

Groups; 1st group is Primary School, 2nd group is High school, 3.group is university, 4th group is Master

In Table 6, the comparison of coach communication skills perceived by team and individual athletes are compared to the athletes in terms of their learning status. According to this, in the coach communication skills perceived by the athletes, the significant difference was found in the learning status of the athletes in terms of the variable of education status ($p < 0.05$). As a result of the LSD test conducted to determine the significant difference between the groups, it was determined that the communication skills of the team and individual athletes were higher than those of the primary and high school students.

Table 7: Relationship between perceived coach communication skills in team and individual athletes with some personal characteristics

	The Level of Perceived Communication Skills of Coach			
	Team		Individual	
	r	p	r	p
Age of the athletes	-.178**	.001	.043	.388
Age of the Coach	.148**	.005	-.044	.379
The Year of Doing Sports	.220**	.000	-.130**	.008
The duration of coaching	-.035	.515	.026	.598
The work duration of the same coach	.154**	.004	.031	.530

As seen in Table 7, there is a weak association between the coach communication skills perceived by team athletes and the athlete's age in the negative direction. It can be said that as the age of team athletes increases, the perceived coach communication skills decrease. Coach communication skills perceived by team athletes were found to be weak in the positive direction between coach age, the year of doing sports and the duration of working with the same coach. As the age of coaches, the years of sports making athletes, and the duration of work with the same coach increase, the coach communication skills perceived by team athletes also increase.

There was no correlation between the coach communication skills perceived by team athletes and the duration of working with the same coach. There were no correlation between coach communication skills perceived by individual athletes and age of athlete, age of coach, duration of coaching and duration of coaching.

It was found a weak relationship in negative direction between coach communication skills perceived by individual athletes and the years of athletes' doing sports. It can be said that as the years of individual athletes' doing sports increases, perceived communication skills of coach decrease.

4. Discussion and Result

In this study that has been conducted to investigate the communication skills of the coaches according to the perceptions of the athletes dealing with individual and team sports, positive results were obtained in terms of branch statues and various variables. Considering the scores obtained by the communication skills of the coach, while coach communication skills perceived by both groups was found to be high ($X_{team}=110.43$, $X_{individual}=116.77$), it was found that coach communication skills perceived by the individual athletes the trainer communication skills perceived by the individual athletes were higher.

In the original study conducted by Abakay (2010), it was found that the communication skills of the athletes with their coaches were high. Yılmaz (2008) also stated in his study that the communication levels of the footballers are generally high. This finding is in parallel with our study.

In statistical analyzes performed on the basis of gender also achieved meaningful results in favor of individual athletes. It can be said that this result is caused by the fact that a coach is interested in individual sports with an athlete and the communication channels are used more effectively. Looking to the comparison of coach communication skills perceived by team athletes and individual athletes in terms of gender variable, it was reached to the result that there was no difference in perceived levels of coach communication skills in terms of gender variable. In a study conducted on athletes with different branch status, coach-athlete relations were not different in terms of gender variation (Selağzı and Çepikkurt 2014).

When the coach communication skills perceived by the team and individual athletes were compared in terms of the variable of education status of the athletes, it was found difference in terms of educational status variable ($p < 0.05$). In both team athletes and individual athletes, the level of communication perceived by trainers of university and graduate students was higher than that of primary and high school students. In parallel with our study, in also a study conducted on amateur and professional soccer players, it was found that the trainer communication skills perceived by those with high educational level were high (Abakay 2010).

This is parallel to the studies carried out in literature (Yılmaz 2008, Abakay and Kuru 2011, Yılmaz et al 2009). From this point of view, as the level of education of the athletes increases, the way of perception of their coaches and their approaches can be more positive and this can give a positive contribution to communication.

The relationship between the coach communication skills perceived by the team athletes with the variables such as athlete's age, coach age, and the year of doing sports, duration of coaching and the duration of working with the same coach were examined. It has been determined that as the ages of team athletes increase, the perceived coach communication skills decrease. Turiel (1983) stated that students with high age had significantly higher communication skills than the others. In Abakay and Kuru (2011)'s study, it is stated that as the age of the athletes increases, the communication skills with their coaches increase. Besides, in our study it has been found that as the age of the coaches increases, the coach communication skills perceived by team athletes have also increased. From these results, it can be said that as the age of the individuals is getting increased (for the coach and the athlete), the communication channels can be used better and the communication between the individuals is more positive. We see that there are results having no difference in literature (Altıntaş et al., Selađzı and Çepikkurt, 2014).

It has been determined that the coach communication skills perceived increases as the team athletes' years of doing sport increase. There was no correlation between the coach communication skills perceived by team athletes and the duration of coaching. In our study, as the duration of working with the same coach increases, coach communication skills perceived in team athletes also increase.

In his study, Yılmaz (2008) has found that the average of those working for 5 years and over was lower than those working for 3 years according to the duration of working with the coach. He stated that the difference may be due to personality traits of the footballers or coaches participating in the study.

Abakay (2010) concluded that there was a significant increase in the communication level with the increase of the working time with the same coach. There was no relation to between the coach communication skills perceived by individual athletes and the age of the athlete, the age of the coach, the duration of the coaching and the duration of working with the same coach. Only a moderate relation was found in the negative direction in the sporting year variable. Therefore, it can be said that as the number of doing sports of the individual athletes increases, coach communication skills perceived decreases. This can be due to the fact that the year of doing sports of these athletes increases, their experiences also develop in that direction and that the coach is referred to the thought such as disagree or dislike of the coach's behavior.

In conclusion, in this study we carried out to determine the coach communication skills perceived by individual athletes and team athletes and to reveal the differences in terms of various variables, it was found that this ratio significantly differentiated to individual athletes while the coach communication skills perceived by

the two athletic groups were high. It has been reached to the findings that the perceived coach communication skills decrease as the years of doing sports increase in individual athletes. While there is no gender difference in athletes in both statues, communication has been seen to increase when the educational status increase. In the case that there is an increase in the variables such as age of the athlete, age of the coach and duration of working with the same coach in the team athletes, the perceived coach communication skills increase.

5. Recommendations

It should be made activities to increase the communication of coaches and athletes in sports clubs. Psychological performance consultants, who work specific to the sport field, should be exercised in the sports clubs. Particularly in team sports, the studies towards increasing the intimacy between athletes and coaches and their communication.

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